

ADVANTAGES OF TOURISM IN JIZZAKH REGION

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Abstract. Questions for Knowledge Control The article describes the tourism potential of the region in Jizzakh Uzbekistan through its natural potential and directions of its presentation of attractive brands that attract tourists, as well as its institutional basis.

Keywords: Tourist areas, recreation, cultural and historical heritage, visas, infrastructure, pilgrimage, tourist areas and villages, examples of brands.

Tourism industry as one of the strategic industries in our country comprehensive development measures are being implemented step by step is increasing. Also, sustainable socio-economic development of regions rapid development of domestic tourism as one of the most important factors, tourists cultural and historical heritage and natural resources of our country, attract tourists introduction of attractive regional brands is its basis as liberalization of the visa regime, registration of foreign citizens the simplification of the procedure, granting of privileges and preferences for the development of the tourism network will allow effective promotion of the national tourism potential in domestic and foreign markets. However, the preliminary analyzes carried out showed the imperfection of the legal framework regulating the tourism industry, the rules for the provision of special tourism services, as well as the uniqueness of the nature of our country for the people of the developed world, the existence of touristic facilities in many regions, moreover, it shows that there is no information about the regional brands that attract with their charm.

That is why the diversity of the world is the basis of the tourism resource tourism objects can attract international tourism enthusiasts only through advertising and promotion. In turn, it is worth noting that the introduction of the tourism industry and its development does not happen to any country in the world, because tourism to this industry the demand for its products in the market is a direct economic need not determined by social needs. Within social needs the need for pilgrimage and recreation is 3 times more than the need for housing in the human psyche. That is the urgency of developing this sector in our country. Acknowledging that the tourism industry is a profitable and, therefore, a less demanding activity, it is appropriate to conduct continuous research on the development and improvement of this industry in our country. One of these ways is the provision of tourist services to residents in densely populated areas with moderate climatic conditions. to create and thereby ecotourism, agrotourism are local brands that serve to meet the daily needs of tourists, including local milk and meat products, as well as delicious national dishes.

Based on such institutional opportunities created in our country, Jizzakh region has extensive opportunities for tourism development. Jizzakh region is located in the central region of Uzbekistan, and because of this, it has the opportunity to conduct a large-scale economy in all directions. Its length is 180 km from east to west, i.e. from Yangiabad district to Farish district, 175 km from south to north, i.e. from Bakhmal district to Mirzachol district.

is The area is 21.1 thousand square kilometers. Of this, 4.8 thousand sq. km. (22.7%) are lands used in agriculture. The area of forests and forestry-related crops is 1.8 thousand (8.5%) sq. km. Chimkortog and Molguzar, extending most of its territory from east to west and partly to northwest, Nurota ridge mountains extending from west to east, east-south and south, from Chordora in Kazakhstan from the north to It forms Aydarkol, which stretches from the northwest of the region to the territory of Navoi region.

In this ancient land, the symbol of the solar year of the ancient Turks is the symbol of the solar year of the ancient Turks - "Solar Calendar", ("Calendar of the Sacs"), which shows the ingenuity and potential of our ancestors in this ancient land. . Shrines like Sa'd ibn Waqqas, Usmat ota, Novqa ota, Khojamushkent ota, Parpi ota, Saifin ota, Savruk ota, Qulfisar ota serve to develop pilgrimage tourism in the region.

It is worth noting that there is an opportunity to get 16-20 million m³ of water per year from the natural springs here. Most of all, precipitation will be relatively abundant in the mountainous areas of Bakhmal, Zomin, Gallaorol districts and Sh.Rashidov and Forish districts of the region. Also, due to the moderate temperature, there is relatively little water fragmentation in Bakhmal, Gallaorol and Forish hollows, Zominsoy, Yettikechuv and Korpasoy.

Development of tourism and recreation clusters in the region there are significant opportunities for it, that is, it is unique to the nature of the region one of the features of mountains and mountain slopes is iron, sulfur, one with hydrogen, radium, silicic acid, carbon dioxide, and alkaline thermo-minerals There are many healing water sources.

In fact, at the moment, there are sanatoriums named "Marjonsuv", "Birshagan", "Gagarin" that treat with such balneological waters in Gallaorol, Forish, Mirzachol districts of the region. At the same time, there are rich mineral sources in Zomin, Jizzakh, Bakhmal districts of the region. According to the chemical and balneological composition of all mineral waters in the region, the most natural uniqueness is directly related to the mountain zone that occupies a large part of the territory. On the mountain slopes of these regions, there are different beautiful natural corners, juniper groves, almond groves, walnut groves, healing meadows, streams, clear waters, and even a layer of pure fresh air. There are rare species of plants and animals and birds in the hills and streams of the huge gorges. Hills and hills in Bakhmal and Zomin districts, huge parks, as well as mineral water at an altitude of 2600 meters above sea level in Bakhmal, People's Park and nature reserves, wonderful waterfalls, dozens of springs on the slopes of the mountains attract humanity. it is a gift of a benevolent nature that beckons.

The nature of the 48,000-hectare People's Park in Zomin district, which is considered the main foundation of tourism clusters in the region, is very beautiful. In the summer and spring, the air layer is painted in the color of the rainbow on the slopes of the mountain, which is 4,000 meters above sea level. Thick juniper forests and huge gorges, floodwaters in streams seem to show a real natural exhibition of nature. Of course, the characteristic of such processes is that people always feel the need for natural corners that are often unexploited and untouched by human hands. The Zomin Nature Reserve was established near the People's Park. The total area of the People's Park and the reserve is 78,000 hectares. In this reserve there are more than 100 medicinal and medicinal plants, animals like white-clawed bear, wild boar, badger, alkar, (mountain goat), jayra, rodents, hawk, black crane, vulture, harrier, There are more than 150 species of birds such as partridges and grouse. "Zomin" sanatorium,

Oriklisi recreation center, and many guest houses for tourists operate in this nature reserve. For this reason, the flow of vacationers, tourists, that is, recreationists, does not stop in these recreational areas throughout the year.

The relief of the region is lowlands in the north, northwest, desert and animals in connection with the rise from the steppes to the hills and mountains types are also increasing. Also for the development of fishing industry in the region there are large-scale opportunities, in particular, in Aydarkol-Tuzkon Arnasoy lakes there are types of fish such as zogora, lakka, suzak and eel. This is surprising the point is that Aydarkol-Tuzkon Arnasoy lakes are the fishing industry in the region at the same time as development, it also serves to develop recreation.

The natural climate of the region is extremely moderate. Summer is dry and hot, winter relatively soft. The summer season is slightly cooler in the mountainous regions of Bakhmal, partially Zomin, Forish districts. The hottest month of the year is June-July in the desert zone, July-August in the mountain zone. Day length is 15 hours in summer and 9 hours in winter. In January, the temperature is +1+4 degrees, and in July it is +26+28 degrees. Annual rainfall is 400-500 mm. The vegetation period is 240-260 days. Air humidity is 70-80% in winter. Sunny days in a year are around 2800-3000 hours. The first snow falls mostly in October. The relative integrity of the territory of the region and its proximity to subtropical latitudes ensure the uniformity of the temperature regime. During the year, on average, 250-270 days the air is clear and the sky is clear. From February to November, solar energy will be relatively more. The total air temperature reaches 5,500 degrees in the southern lowlands and 4,3-4,500 degrees in the northern lowlands. Precipitation in the territory of the region falls mainly in the winter and spring seasons. Precipitation increases from north to south. The amount of annual precipitation exceeds 295 mm in Mirzachol, which is 276 meters high, and 400 mm in Sangzor, which is 392 meters high. The number of days that snow remains in a year is 20-22 days in the plains and 60-70 days in the mountainous regions. Annual rainfall in the flat part of the region is 200 mm. around. The rate of evaporation is 100-120 mm. In the territory of the region, there is a strong wind from the north-west from time to time. In April and May, there are cases of strong wind, hail and hail. The population of the region reached 1,403,100 people as of January 2021 and increased by 29,700 people or 102.2% from the beginning of the year. Of these, 647,900 people live in urban areas (46.2%) and 755,200 people live in rural areas (53.8%). According to its composition, there are representatives of more than 70 nationalities. Uzbeks make up 83 percent of the total population. The average density is one sq. km. 65.5 people.

As can be seen from the above data, the population is 163,600 people in Zomin district of the region (11.8% of the population of the region), Bakhmal district with a population of 155.8 thousand people (11.3% of the population of the region), Gallaorol district with a population of 171.4 thousand people (12.4% of the population of the region has extensive opportunities for organizing tourist guest houses with recreation, as well as tourism clusters based on their mutual cooperation. From the above information, it can be said that currently, not only in our country, but also in the whole world, the tourism industry is a low-cost, but profitable industry. This field is considered a supporter of some attractiveness, requiring appropriate culture, ethics, and aesthetics. In addition to the economic aspects of the tourism sector, it is necessary to highlight its social and spiritual aspects.

That is, there is an opportunity to earn income with less work compared to some, for example, the construction industry, which requires a lot of labor, which corresponds to 1 soum of labor. From a social point of view, the service workers working in this field at the same time enjoy the products of this field while providing services to tourists, which in turn causes the extension of human life. Spiritually, through the development of the tourism sector, there is an opportunity to strengthen the position of our country on the world map by showing our architectural monuments, which are the symbols of our national values inherited from our ancestors, to the whole world.

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